

Net Zero Industry Innovation Centre (Teesside University):

Breaking down barriers to net zero data sharing

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Topic overview

This case study explores how work carried out by Hannah Stothard and the **Net Zero Industry Innovation Centre (NZIIC)** at Teesside University aims to enable responsible data sharing to accelerate decarbonisation. Centred on a region with a rich industrial history and ambitious net zero redevelopment plans, the work examines how sustainable data governance and community-led frameworks can promote collaboration between businesses, researchers and policymakers, while addressing the cultural hesitancy that often prevents organisations from sharing the data needed to create systemic change.

Participation in Bridge AI – The Turing Way Practitioners Hub has influenced this work by helping Hannah focus on key areas such as stakeholder mapping and strategic planning, as well as emphasising the value of collaborative, open approaches.

Decarbonisation needs data – but data needs trust

Teesside has historically been one of the UK's most industrialised regions, home to heavy manufacturing such as shipbuilding, steel, iron and petrochemicals. Today, **the region is positioning itself at the forefront of the UK's net zero transition**, with investment in hydrogen production, carbon capture and storage, offshore wind and alternative fuels.

Hannah Stothard is a former Senior Research Fellow in AI at NZIIC, where she joined The Turing Way Practitioners Hub as an Expert-in-Residence. At NZIIC, Hannah's work sat at the intersection of emerging AI technologies and industrial decarbonisation. Her research highlighted that while there is broad support for net zero ambitions, there is far less comfort with the data sharing required to enable AI-driven insights and turn those ambitions into reality.

Some organisations may be concerned that sharing emissions data could expose under performance, bringing about reputational risk, or threaten intellectual property and ownership. Others are deterred by the potential complexities of data sharing agreements and AI models, lacking the in-house knowledge to engage confidently with the topic. In many cases, the data itself is outdated, duplicated or siloed across supply chains.

"There is also a lot of stakeholder fatigue," adds Hannah, who is also a co-founder of the AI and data innovation consultancy **Seer**. "Teesside and the wider North East is a relatively small region, and so universities and other organisations are repeatedly asking the same pool of people and businesses for their time and data. That repetition becomes a challenge."

Trust and confidence in the process, as well as accessible, easy-to-use mechanisms, are required to convince companies to take part. Hannah's proposed solution is the development of a responsible data-sharing framework designed specifically to support decarbonisation initiatives in industrialised regions. Several existing frameworks provide relevant precedents to support this, including the UK government's 2022 Data Sharing Governance Framework and the World Bank's 2025 Responsible Data Sharing Framework for the Distributed Renewable Energy Sector (Shrestha et al.), the latter offering a useful parallel for industrialised regions beyond the UK. Any such framework will also need to navigate key legal obligations – in particular, UK GDPR, the Data Protection Act 2018, and the ICO's Data Sharing Code of Practice, which together set the core requirements around lawful basis for processing, data minimisation, and accountability.

A responsible data-sharing framework for decarbonisation: the benefits

The proposed framework would:

- enable secure, compliant data exchange between businesses, researchers and public bodies
- reduce duplication across supply chains
- support the generation of new research insights and predictive modelling
- provide clearer governance structures around data ownership, anonymisation and reuse
- facilitate AI-enabled analysis of regional environmental and health impacts.

Hannah offers an example that illustrates a potentially beneficial public health intervention through data sharing and innovation: modelling how wind trajectories interact with industrial emissions, such as ammonia, and how this might affect local health outcomes in areas with historically high rates of respiratory illness. While hypothetical at present, access to the multiple relevant datasets – meteorological, industrial and health – opens up this type of analysis and policy impact. Importantly, the work is intended to extend beyond quantitative datasets to include qualitative research such as surveys and interviews exploring workforce readiness for new fuels and technologies.

The framework is conceived not as a proprietary product owned by a single entity, but instead as community-governed and collaborative – particularly appropriate within the NZIC's pre-competitive innovation environment. At the same time, Hannah recognises that a framework of this kind could have commercial potential, for example, through licensing or implementation support.

Similar existing models include **Catena-X** – the most compelling industrial sector parallel available. Catena-X is the first collaborative data ecosystem for the automotive industry, enabling OEMs, Tier 1 and Tier 2 suppliers to seamlessly exchange product carbon footprint data along the value chain, thereby reducing costs, increasing transparency, and supporting scalable decarbonisation. In a striking practical demonstration of its value, one supplier used Catena-X to calculate carbon footprint using and found a 46% drop in reported emissions – not because previous figures were incorrect, but because primary data replaced averages.

GAia-X/OMEGA-X, meanwhile, adds a European sovereign data infrastructure angle. The EU-funded project aims to implement an energy data space with federated infrastructure, a data marketplace, and a service marketplace, enabling data sharing between different stakeholders while guaranteeing scalability and interoperability.

Another directly relevant but underused precedent comes from the Netherlands. **MIDDEN** (Manufacturing Industry Decarbonisation Data Exchange Network), run by PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency and TNO, is aimed at building a shared, verified knowledge base for industrial decarbonisation options, covering the energy and material consumption of the Dutch manufacturing industry. Its open database supports industry, policymakers, analysts and the energy sector in their common efforts to achieve deep decarbonisation – and the data and reports are publicly available. This is arguably the closest real-world parallel to Hannah’s framework proposal: MIDDEN is applied to a specific industrial region, and its GitHub repository makes it directly citable as an open model.

Proportionality and system reform

The technical and governance design of the framework reflects several tensions and challenges that need to be overcome. For example, even anonymised data can risk ‘jigsaw identification,’ where contextual clues allow individuals or organisations to be inferred (something Hannah encountered when trialling a data-sharing framework on a smaller scale within the maritime sector). Ethical review processes, particularly in academic contexts, can sometimes be so onerous that they slow down or deter potentially beneficial research projects. And while the framework aims to reduce duplication of reporting and analysis across supply chains, the regulatory responsibilities of companies in particular sectors also need to be accommodated.

Hannah argues for greater proportionality when it comes to data sharing, use and governance, including increased opportunities to use or reuse already-collected data, clearer agreements or memoranda of understanding (MOUs) that facilitate responsible sharing, and well-defined API or portal-based data access mechanisms.

She also notes that only **around 1 in 7 UK businesses share digitised data outside of their own organisation**, and fewer still use data for AI-driven decision-making. Addressing this cultural resistance requires framing data sharing not as punitive oversight but as supportive collaboration towards shared decarbonisation goals. Furthermore, Hannah emphasises that adoption will require engagement at multiple organisational levels, from CEOs to software development teams and data security officers. Governance frameworks alone are insufficient – cultural change and literacy-building are essential.

Next steps: Formalising a data-sharing agreement

The responsible data-sharing framework is still at a formative research stage, working towards a minimum viable product or pilot. An important next step will be to explore the creation of an agreement or MOU supported by local industrial networks. Such an agreement would clarify what data can be shared, under what conditions, through which technical mechanisms, and with what governance and accountability structures in place. The aim is to move from informal conversations about collaboration to a more formal framework that organisations feel confident participating in. Hannah adds: “We’re also looking at running a hackathon or community workshop on this topic, to ensure that continued development is open source.”

Alongside this, Hannah is interested in developing API-based access portals that would allow controlled data exchange, and exploring how shared datasets might support AI models tailored to local industrial contexts. In terms of reference points, the **FIWARE open-source Smart Data platform** (used in EU smart city and energy projects) provides a well-documented API framework for IoT and industrial data. **DCAT-AP** (Data Catalogue Vocabulary Application Profile) is the EU standard for cross-portal data interoperability and is widely used in government data portals. In the industrial and energy contexts specifically, strong examples come from the International Energy Agency’s Energy Data collection APIs, the UK’s **National Grid ESO Data Portal**, and the Energy Systems Catapult’s data and digital tools. For emissions and environmental data, the UK’s Environment Agency **Bathing Water API** and the **Defra Data Services Platform** provide accessible real-world examples.

The **East Coast Cluster/Northern Endurance Partnership** (of which NZIIC is part) offers a more localised example. The East Coast Cluster is actively bringing together communities, businesses, industry and academia to deliver carbon capture and storage infrastructure needed to decarbonise Teesside and the Humber. The shared CO₂ transport and monitoring infrastructure being built represents exactly the kind of common technical infrastructure – with data flowing between multiple industrial operators and a shared network operator – that a data portal framework would need to connect to.

Hannah also believes that stronger data agreements could help create a more fertile environment for collaborative projects, which in turn may make it easier to secure support and investment. Longer term, she sees the potential for broader system reform, but acknowledges that progress will depend on incremental trust-building and demonstrating clear, practical value of data sharing.

Reflections on *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub

“The Practitioners Hub came at a really pivotal moment for me, because I was transitioning between roles and rethinking how I approach things. It pushed me to think more critically and practically about AI implementation and data governance. The sessions on stakeholder mapping were particularly powerful because they gave structure to something I’d been doing intuitively, and the strategy development workshop was timely as my new role involved producing a 12-month product roadmap. What I valued most was that the programme didn’t just focus on the business side of things – it dug into the technical and governance foundations such as data readiness and security, responsible AI implementation, and open source. It has reminded me that while AI seems to be moving in the direction of closed models, there’s still real value in collaborative and open approaches if they’re implemented thoughtfully.”

Hannah Stothard,

former Senior Research Fellow in AI
at Teesside University’s Net Zero Industry Innovation Centre.

Key takeaways

- Decarbonisation ambitions require trusted mechanisms for responsible data sharing.
- Cultural resistance can be a greater barrier than technical limitations.
- Proportional, clearly defined data agreements can reduce duplication and enable AI-driven insights.
- Ethical AI implementation requires literacy across entire organisations.
- Community-governed frameworks may offer a viable path in pre-competitive innovation spaces.

Contributors and acknowledgements

This case study is published under *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub* 2025-26 Cohort – case study series. The Practitioners Hub is *The Turing Way* project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2025, The Turing Way team welcomed **Hannah Stothard from Teesside Net Zero Industry Innovation Centre** as an Expert-in-Residence to discuss and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI as well as build additional skills around best practices in responsible, ethical, and collaborative working. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2025-26 Cohort was co-delivered by **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher – Open Source Practices and Dr Ann Borda, Senior Research Community Manager. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager. **Ann Borda** is the Case Study Liaison for this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Malvika Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: theturingway@gmail.com

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